

An Integrated Visible Light and Power Line Communication Approach for Real-Time Weather Parameter Monitoring

^{1,*}Sujit Chatterjee, ²Rubi Baishya

¹Department of Physics, Lumding College, Lumding, Assam, India

²Department of Physics, Behali Degree College, Biswanath, Assam, India

*Corresponding author: sujitc43@gmail.com

Abstract

A hybrid communication system uses different heterogeneous components to solve the issues with the last mile and last inch connectivity. In this paper, a hybrid communication system using visible light and power line is developed. The same is used as a sensor network for monitoring of weather parameters in an indoor setting. The performance of the system both individually and as hybrid are found out in terms of the bit error rate (BER). It is seen that mostly, the power line part adds to the BER and the visible light section allows extended angular coverage. The system enables signal transfer via power line through a maximum distance of 13 m and visible light via 5 m through an angular coverage of 20°. The error in the monitored parameters namely temperature and humidity is negligible compared to the variations in the monitored parameter. The results will be used for future development of an efficient hybrid communication technique for extended usage.

Keywords: *Hybrid Communication System, Power Line Communication, Visible Light Communication, Sensor Networks*

Introduction

Hybrid communication system uses heterogeneous communication links like wired and wireless for last mile and last inch coverage. This involves overcoming the individual shortcomings providing accessibility and data transfer among the various components. A probable wired counterpart would be using the available power line (PL) for communication. This mode of communication is usually called the power line communication (PLC) and offers a cost-effective solution as no extra wiring or cabling are necessary [1]. The wireless counterpart can be Visible Light Communication (VLC) that uses the same light source for illumination to transmit data [2]. VLC usually requires dedicated wired cables to transfer data to the lighting devices. However, the unambiguous PL can also be used for this

as the lighting devices also require power to make it working. Now-a-days PLC, cater to applications in three broad areas: access, in-house and control. Access PLC is the communication outside the home that may be in the Medium Voltage (MV) or Low Voltage (LV) cables. Usually optical fiber, satellite etc. is used to inject the high data signals into the cables. The MV lines pass on the communication signal to the LV lines and then to the House Access Point (HAP). Use of PLC inside the homes is called the in-house PLC [3]. This can be used as high-speed Local Areas Network (LAN) and also enable sharing of resources. In control applications, PLC is used to control instruments and also in smart grid (SG) application. The G.hn standard enables seamless data communication between the four communication channels namely phonenumber, PL, Ethernet and optical fibre. The advantage in using VLC is that it is safe, license free and also secured [4]. This can be used in critical environments like hospitals, petrochemical plants, or airplanes where the use of wireless is restricted [5], [6], [7]. The large bandwidth (BW) of visible light gives a solution to the spectrum crowding problem. The transmitter of light is usually the LED where the same is switched at a far faster rate than the eye can detect.

PLC devices can broadly be divided into two parts depending on the standards used. The standards differentiate the devices according to BW used: namely the Narrowband PLC (NB-PLC) and the Broadband PLC (BPLC). The NB-PLC uses a frequency <500 kHz for low bit rate requirements like control of the order of few kbps. The standards vary with countries like the CENELAC in Europe [8], the FCC in USA [9] and ARIB in Japan [10]. The BPLC standard either uses 2-30 MHz or <100 MHz for high speed data speed requirement [11]. There are two standards that govern VLC i.e. the visible light communication consortium (VLCC) in Japan and the IEEE 802.15.7 standard [2].

Review of papers show that much work has been done on PLC and VLC individually but very less work is done when it comes to hybridization [12], [13], [14]. However, such an infrastructure is necessary owing to the initiatives and present demands of SGs, smart homes, Internet of Things (IoT) etc. In this paper, a hybrid communication system is developed using PLC and VLC with specific application to indoor weather monitoring. A weather monitoring prototype (WMP) is developed that uses PLC, VLC and PLC-VLC modems for data transfer and tested in a Small Office Home Office (SOHO) setup. The efficiency of the system is studied in terms of the BER and error in the monitored parameters. The whole system can also be termed as a Sensor network (SN) using hybrid communication schemes. The band used for the hybrid setup is <500 kHz which lies in the FCC band.

The paper is sectioned as follows; Section 2 of the paper presents in brief, the need of a SN and the work targeted in this paper. In Section 3, the characteristics of a PLC network in terms of noise and channel capacity (CC) are analyzed. In Section 4, the hybrid communication system is presented

in detail. Section 5 discussed the performances in terms of BER and the monitored parameters. The paper then concludes with future aims of the work.

Sensor Networks, weather parameter monitoring and hybrid communication

The communication infrastructure, connecting localized or distributed sensor nodes all together for monitoring and recording data is known as SN. SN consists of four basic components: an assembly of localized or distributed sensors, connecting network (wired or wireless), central point for the collection of the data and computing center for data evaluation. SN helps the administration to monitor, observe and to take action to an event and phenomena in a specific environment. Monitoring of weather parameters (both outdoor and indoor) like temperature, humidity, pressure, rainfall, wind speed etc are necessary for knowledge of weather condition in a particular area. This is indispensable for maximizing agricultural output and in industries, airports, hospitals, smart homes etc. The communication mode may be wireless communication modes (Bluetooth, Wi-Fi, Radio-Frequency (RF) 418/433 MHz, 900 MHz, etc) or through a wired network (e.g. Ethernet, Optical fiber etc.). Wired sensors network provides reliable data recording; however they can also require costly installation and replacement/reinstallation problems when the system is needed to be shift to another location. The wireless systems also have some disadvantages like limited by distance, drainage of battery, high replacement cost, need of extra wiring etc. A hybrid communication system can be the best option being used as a SN [12], [13], [14]. One of the components of this can be the readily available PL and the other visible light. The transmitter with the sensor nodes and the receiver can be connected to any of the distributed outlets available in indoor PL scenario and visible light can act as a wireless section for last inch coverage (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: A hybrid sensor network using PLC and VLC

Noise analysis in indoor power line channels and estimation of channel capacity

In this section, a preliminary analysis of noise in an indoor PL channel is done for estimation of CC. Such a study is the prerequisite of developing any communication system as this determines many communication parameters like BER, band of transmission and the modulation technique used. Such an analysis is indispensable for PL channels as the noise is known to be non Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN). The AWGN is commonly used by communication systems as the noise model. PL noise is usually constituted of three classes: background noise (BGN), impulsive noise and narrowband interferences (NBI) [15]. BGN is the component that is always present in the total noise and always has a low power spectral density (PSD). The impulsive noise occurs above the BGN and can be synchronous or asynchronous to the mains. The NBI occur due to the transmission frequencies of radio centers. As the AC line has a power signal of 50 Hz, 230 V, measuring instruments cannot be directly connected to the line. It requires efficient high pass filters that can filter off the 50 Hz frequencies and pass the high frequency noise signal to the devices un-attenuated. In order to study the noise, a coupler is designed that has these qualities (Fig. 2). The coupler consists of a 1:1 transformer (TR) and capacitors (C1 and C2) in series with some protection devices. The windings of the transformer are bifilar and the core is soft iron so that the resonance frequency is very high and it offers nearly constant frequency response to up-to 10 MHz. The cut off frequency of the coupler is 100 kHz with a roll of rate of ~25 dB. The experimental setup to capture the PL noise consists of the coupler connected to the phase neutral pair of an indoor PL in one side and to a Mixed Signal Oscilloscope (Keysight, InfinitiVision MSOX2024A, 200 MHz, 2 GSa/a) on the other side. The MSO is controlled by a PC and noise acquisition is in an indoor PL setting in the University campus done after a period of 5 minutes for an extended period of time. The acquired noise is analyzed offline. The PSD is found to decrease with frequency as shown in Fig. 3 and nearly flat above 1 MHz. The noise detected was mainly the BGN.

Fig. 2: Experimental setup for PL noise data acquisition.

Fig. 3: PSD of captured PL noise

The PSD of the noise $N(f)$ can be modeled using a four-parameter equation given by (1) after testing with higher order exponentials. Such a model is also opted in other papers [16].

$$N(f) = ae^{bf} + ce^{df} \quad \dots(1)$$

Here the model parameters are given by a, b, c, d and the frequency in Hz is f . This model is useful in estimating the CC using the water filling approach (WFA) [17], [18], [19]. The WFA is applicable for all types of noise (white or non-white) with a flat or non-flat transfer function. The approach considers the power to be distributed in the entire BW just as water would be distributed in the bottom of a bucket as given by (2) (Fig. 4)

$$S_y(f) = \begin{cases} B - \frac{N(f)}{|H(f)|^2} & ; f \in F_B \\ 0 & ; f \notin F_B \end{cases} \quad \dots(2)$$

In (2), the band of frequencies for which (7) is satisfied is termed as F_B .

$$\frac{N(f)}{|H(f)|^2} \leq B \quad \dots(3)$$

Fig. 4: Water filling approach for estimation of the channel capacity

During analysis, as the transmit signal power is increased, the situation lies in either of two cases: Case-1 or Case -2. In Case-1, as the transmit power is small, so that the entire BW is not applicable to add to the capacity. In such case, the CC is given by (4).

$$C(y) = \int_y^{f_{max}} \log_2 \left(\frac{N(y)}{N(f)} \right) df \quad \dots(4)$$

Where $N(y)$ is the noise at frequency y , and is the frequency where (5) is satisfied

$$S_y(f) = B - N(y) = 0 ; f_{min} < y < f_{max} \quad \dots(5)$$

However, when the transmit power is large, (Case-2), the entire available BW is used for capacity and is given by (6).

$$C(y) = \int_{f_{min}}^{f_{max}} \log_2 \left(\frac{N(y)}{N(f)} \right) df \quad \dots (6)$$

Here, f_{min} and f_{max} are the minimum and maximum frequencies in the BW of observation.

Using this approach, the CC for the indoor PL channel is estimated for different transmits power (P_t) and different attenuation (α). The maximum transmit power used is 0.5 W as very high values would cause the PL to act as an antenna radiating the signal into space. The attenuation is taken to be frequency flat which is actually not so because of frequency selective nature of the PL channel. The constant value however gives the worst case of frequency selectivity. The CC for different bands (<500 kHz, 280-480 kHz, 330-430 kHz), transmit power (0.2-0.5 Watt) and attenuation (0-10 dB) as given as in Table 1. As seen from the table, the CC is quite high of the order of Mbps even in a small BW of 100 kHz and attenuation of 10 dB. As weather parameters are slowly changing quantities, low bit rates suffice for efficient monitoring. As such a bandwidth of 280-480 kHz is used in the PLC-VLC WMP.

Table.1: The channel capacity using the noise in power line channels

BW (kHz)	P_t (Watt)	α (dB)	CC (Mbps)	Band used
500	0.5	0	6.08	Entire FCC
		5	4.36	
		10	3.63	
500	0.4	0	4.70	Entire FCC
		5	3.01	
		10	2.21	
500	0.3	0	4.50	Entire FCC
		5	2.80	
		10	2.00	

500	0.2	0	4.20	Entire FCC
		5	2.60	
		10	1.67	
200	0.5	0	5.20	280 kHz-480 kHz
100	0.5	0	2.20	330 kHz-430 kHz

Design of the hybrid communication setup

The hybrid communication system consists of a PLC modem, a PLC-VLC hybrid modem and a VLC modem as shown in Fig. 5. The sensor that does the weather monitoring consists of a temperature sensor (LM 35) and humidity sensor (DHT 11) placed at transmitter of the PLC modem. The sensor signals are converted to serial data bit stream using an arduino board (μC). The baud rate chosen is 1200. The transmitter consists of sensor in a μC , a frequency Shift keying (FSK) modulator, a power amplifier and a transmitting coupler. In FSK modulation, digital signal is transmitted by discrete change in frequency of the carrier wave [17]. The cut off frequency of the coupler is 100 kHz. The transmitting coupler is connected to the phase neutral combination of an indoor PL. The receiver section consists of a combination of PLC/VLC modem termed as PLC and VLC modem. The PLC part consists of a coupler (cut off=120 kHz) and a FSK demodulator which is a Phase Lock Loop (PLL). The output of the PLL is fed into the LED driver which drives the LED. The LED used is a 1 watt white LED that is phosphor converted (pc converted LED) and then adequately transferred to intensity modulation [2], [4]. The receiver part of the VLC modem placed at a distance of 5 m from the transmitter. The specific characteristics of the modem are given in Table 2. The distance of the PL through which the data transmission is tested is $d_{PL}=13$ m. The maximum distance for VLC is $d_{VLC}=5$ m with a maximum angular deviation of $\Phi=20^{\circ}$. The BER using the setup is found out both by transmitting known bits and also data from the sensors.

Fig. 5: Experimental setup of the hybrid communication system used as a sensor network

Table.2: The specifications and characteristics of the components used in the design of the hybrid system

Block	Component	Characteristics
Sensor	LM 35, DHT 11	---
μ C	Arduino	---
FSK modulator	XR2206	Space: 370 kHz Mark: 397.5 kHz
Power amplifier	BD 139	Power: 0.5 W
Coupler 1 Coupler 2	Transformer, Capacitor	Cut off 1: 100 kHz Cut off 2: 120 kHz
FSK de-modulator	LM 565	Free running: 380 kHz Lock range: 320-450 kHz
LED driver	BD 139	V_{cc} =5 Volt
LED	White	Pc converted, 1 W
Photodetector	BPW 34	---
Pre-amplifier	LF356	Slew rate: 12 Volt/ μ S

Results and discussion

In order to test the efficiency of the system serial bit of stream 01010101 corresponding to ASCII “U” is initially transmitted. For different PLC distance d_{PL} and each angle Φ of the VLC setup as well as different VLC distance d_{VLC} , the BER is found out for the PLC part (BER_{PLC}), VLC part (BER_{VLC}) and the combined PLC-VLC part ($BER_{PLC-VLC}$). Table 3 gives the BER for different transmit power P_t , Φ and d_{VLC} . The distance d_{PL} is kept constant. It is seen from the table that the error in the data communication through the PLC-VLC modem is mainly occurring because of the PLC part and the VLC does not cause any error in the communication. The maximum error of the modem is found to be $BER_{PLC-VLC}=7 \times 10^{-1}$ at $P_t=0.2$ Watt. It is also seen that the maximum angle through which communication is possible is 20° and a variation upto this does not cause any increase in the BER compared to the 0° position. Beyond 20° , the received intensity is very less to be detected by the photodiode. This is also the case for the length of VLC channel greater than 5 m. The BER is found out by comparing each of the transmitted and received digital bits (1s and 0s), present in the ASCII character. In future the error starting from LSB to MSB will be analyzed individually.

Using the VLC-PLC setup, monitoring of temperature and humidity is done for maximum $d_{PL}=13$ m, $d_{VLC}=5$ m, and $\Phi=20^\circ$. For every monitoring event, 50 temperature and humidity data is transmitted and the received at the monitoring device. The mean of the data is noted in Table 4 and Table 5 respectively. In the tables, T_T , R_T , T_H and R_H are the mean transmitted temperature, received

temperature, transmitted humidity and received humidity respectively. It is observed that a maximum error of 1.18 °C and 2.31 RH is obtained at a minimum power of 0.2 Watt. However increasing the transmit power decreases the error to zero.

The experimental setup has been successfully used for a maximum 13 m PL distance. Beyond this the noise in the PL is much more than the received signal strength.

Table. 3: The BER of different test channels of the power line and visible light section

P_t (Watt)	d_{PL} (m)	BER _{PL}	d_{VLC} (m)	Φ	BER _{VLC}	BER _{PLC-VLC}
0.2	13	7×10^{-1}	2	0°	0	7×10^{-1}
				20°	0	7×10^{-1}
			5	0°	0	7×10^{-1}
				20°	0	7×10^{-1}
0.3	13	1.8×10^{-1}	2	0°	0	1.8×10^{-1}
				20°	0	1.8×10^{-1}
			5	0°	0	1.8×10^{-1}
				20°	0	1.8×10^{-1}
0.5	13	0	2	0°	0	0
				20°	0	0
			5	0°	0	0
				20°	0	0

Table.4: The transmitted and the received temperature using the PLC-VLC setup

P_t (Watt)	d_{PL} (m)	d_{VLC} (m)	Φ	T _T (°C)	R _T (°C)	Error (°C)
0.2	13	2	0°	36.08	37.20	1.12
			20°	36.54	37.72	1.18
		5	0°	35.99	37.12	1.13
			20°	36.12	36.99	0.87
0.3	13	2	0°	36.20	36.79	0.59
			20°	36.86	36.22	0.64
		5	0°	36.47	37.02	0.55
			20°	36.27	36.75	0.48
0.5	13	2	0°	36.18	36.18	0
			20°	36.99	36.99	0
		5	0°	36.78	36.78	0
			20°	36.51	36.51	0

Table.5: The transmitted and the received humidity using the PLC-VLC setup

P_t (Watt)	d_{PL} (m)	d_{VLC} (m)	Φ	T_H (RH %)	R_H (RH %)	Error (%)
0.2	13	2	0°	73.11	75.42	2.31
			20°	73.82	76.02	2.2
		5	0°	72.99	75.23	2.24
			20°	73.25	75.28	2.03
0.3	13	2	0°	73.20	74.13	0.93
			20°	73.82	74.69	0.87
		5	0°	74.54	73.85	0.69
			20°	74.28	74.80	0.52
0.5	13	2	0°	73.11	73.11	0
			20°	73.54	73.54	0
		5	0°	73.65	73.65	0
			20°	73.88	73.88	0

Conclusion

In this paper a hybrid SN is developed using PLC and VLC. Although there is error in the monitored parameter, this is negligible as the transmitted data also varies within limits. However further modification in both the modems are necessary for mitigating the individual problems like high time varying noise, non-white noise especially occurring in the PLs, frequency selectivity of PL channels and limitations caused due to attenuations and detection [15], [16], [19]. For example, a Digital Signal Processor (DSP) can be used for adaptive noise removal, and an Automatic Gain Controller (AGC) can be used to increase the angular coverage and distance for the VLC. In the future, such a system will be developed for extended coverage in a practical SOHO setup.

References

- [1] Wang, D., Song, Y., & Wang, X. (2017). Channel modeling of broadband powerline communications. In *Proc. 2017 IEEE 9th Int. Conf. Communication Software and Networks (ICCSN)* (pp. 427-430). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCSN.2017.8230149>
- [2] Khan, L. U. (2017). Visible light communication: Applications, architecture, standardization and research challenges. *Digit. Commun. Netw.*, 3(2), 78-88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dcan.2016.07.004>
- [3] Tiru, B. (2015). Exploiting power line for communication purpose: Features and prospects of power line communication. In *Intelligent Applications for Heterogeneous System Modeling and Design* (pp. 320-334). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-4666-8493-5.ch014>
- [4] Tanaka, Y., Komine, T., Haruyama, S., & Nakagawa, M. (2001). Indoor visible communication utilizing plural white LEDs as lighting. In *Proc. 12th IEEE Int. Symp. Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Commun. (PIMRC)* (Vol. 2, pp. F81-F85). <https://doi.org/10.1109/PIMRC.2001.965300>
- [5] Tan, Y. Y., Jung, S. J., & Chung, W. Y. (2013). Real time biomedical signal transmission of mixed ECG signal and patient information using visible light communication. In *Proc. Annu. Int. Conf. IEEE Eng. Med. Biol. Soc. (EMBC)* (pp. 4791-4794). <https://doi.org/10.1109/EMBC.2013.6610619>
- [6] Chang, S. H. (2015). A visible light communication link protection mechanism for smart factory. In *Proc. IEEE 29th Int. Conf. Advanced Information Networking and Applications Workshops (WAINA)* (pp. 733-737). <https://doi.org/10.1109/WAINA.2015.41>
- [7] Singla, A., Sharma, D., & Vashisth, S. (2017). Data connectivity in flights using visible light communication. In *Proc. Int. Conf. Computing and Communication Technologies for Smart Nation (IC3TSN)* (pp. 71-74). <https://doi.org/10.1109/IC3TSN.2017.8284453>
- [8] European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization. (2010, September). *Signalling on low-voltage electrical installations in the frequency range 3 kHz to 148.5 kHz - Part 1: General requirements, frequency bands and electromagnetic disturbances* (EN 50065-1). [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=OJ%3AC%3A2009%3A126%3AFULL>
- [9] Federal Communications Commission. (2008). *Title 47 CFR Part 15 - Radio Frequency Devices*. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-47/chapter-I/subchapter-A/part-15>
- [10] Association of Radio Industries and Businesses. (2002, November). *Power line communication equipment (10 kHz-450 kHz)* (ARIB STD-T84, ver. 1.0). [Online]. Available: https://www.arib.or.jp/english/std_tr/telecommunications/desc/std-t84.html
- [11] IEEE Standards Association. (1990). *IEEE Guide for the Interconnection of User-Owned Substations to Electric Utilities* (IEEE Std 1109-1990). [Online]. Available: <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/1109/1676/>
- [12] Ma, H., Lampe, L., & Hranilovic, S. (2017, August). Hybrid visible light and power line communication for indoor multiuser downlink. *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.*, 9(8), 635-647. <https://doi.org/10.1364/JOCN.9.000635>
- [13] Yang, L., Li, J., & Zhang, J. (2017). Hybrid visible light communications (VLC) and PLC system. In *Proc. Opto-Electronics and Communications Conf. (OECC) and Photonics Global Conf. (PGC)* (pp. 1-2). <https://doi.org/10.1109/OECC.2017.8114968>
- [14] Ma, H., Lampe, L., & Hranilovic, S. (2016). Subcarrier allocation in hybrid visible light and power line communication system. In *Proc. IEEE Int. Symp. Circuits and Systems (ISCAS)* (pp. 2819-2822). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCAS.2016.7539179>

